

Survey: Cooling Energy Consumption in Housings © 2024 Monaya Syam is licensed under CC BY-SA 4.0

Please confirm your acceptance to take part in this survey.

- I consent to taking part in this survey
- I do not consent (If “I do not consent”: End of survey)

Part 1:

1. Are you an expatriate living in Al Ain city?

- Yes
- No (If “No”: End of survey with a message explaining why the survey ends here)

2. How old are you?

- Under 18 (If “Under 18”: End of survey with a message explaining why the survey ends here)
- 18-24
- 25-34
- 35-44
- 45-54
- 55-64
- 65 or above

3. Select your gender.

- Female
- Male
- Prefer not to say

4. Select your nationality.

----- (a drop list)

5. In which year did you come for the first time to the United Arab Emirates to work and/or live?

----- (a drop list)

6. Did you live in another country before living in the UAE?

- Yes
- No
- Prefer not to say

Follow-up question (If question 6 answer is “Yes”):

6.a. Where did you live before coming to the United Arab Emirates?

----- (a drop list)

7. What is the highest level of educational qualification you hold?

- Uneducated
- Below high school level
- High school

- University degree
- Post-graduate
- Prefer not to say

8. What is your occupation or study subject?

----- (a drop list)

Follow-up question (If question 8 answer is “Other”):

8.a. Please specify.

9. Do you work?

- Yes
- No
- I am retired
- I am studying
- Prefer not to say

Follow-up question (If question 9 answer is “Yes”):

9.a. When do you typically work in the workplace/your office outside home? *Please choose all options that apply.*

- Morning (6:00 am – 12:00 pm)
- Afternoon (12:00 pm – 5:00 pm)
- Evening (5:00 pm – 9:00 pm)
- Night (9:00 pm – 6:00 am)
- I do not work in office or workplace
- Prefer not to say

9.b. Do you work from home?

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes
- Prefer not to say

Follow-up question (If question 9.b. answer is “Yes” or “Sometimes”):

9.b.a. When do you typically work from home? *Please choose all options that apply.*

- Morning (6:00 am – 12:00 pm)
- Afternoon (12:00 pm – 5:00 pm)
- Evening (5:00 pm – 9:00 pm)
- Night (9:00 pm – 6:00 am)
- Prefer not to say

10. Which part of the day do you typically spend at home? *Please choose all options that apply.*

- Morning (6:00 am – 12:00 pm)

- Afternoon (12:00 pm – 5:00 pm)
- Evening (5:00 pm – 9:00 pm)
- Night (9:00 pm – 6:00 am)
- Prefer not to say

11. How many people live in your home?

----- (a drop list)

12. Are there children aged less than 18 years old living in the home?

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes
- Other
- Prefer not to say

Follow-up question (If question 12 answer is “Sometimes” or “Other”):

12.a. Please define.

Follow-up questions (If question 12 answer is “Yes” or “Sometimes” or “Other”):

12.b. When children are usually at home? *Please choose all options that apply.*

- Morning (6:00 am – 12:00 pm)
- Afternoon (12:00 pm – 5:00 pm)
- Evening (5:00 pm – 9:00 pm)
- Night (9:00 pm – 6:00 am)
- Prefer not to say

12.c. Where do children usually stay most of the time at home?

- In their bedrooms
- In the living room
- In a study room at home
- In a play area inside home
- Other
- Prefer not to say

Follow-up question (If question 12.c. answer is “Other”):

12.c.a. Please specify.

13. What is the type of house you currently live in?

*Villa in a compound in this context is defined as a single-family housing unit located within a gated residential compound. **Villa that is not part of a compound** is any single-family housing unit that is not part of a residential compound and is not part of a multi-storey residential building. **Apartment** is a home as part of a multi-storey residential building consisting of multiple apartments distributed among multiple floors.*

- Villa in a compound
- Villa that is not part of a compound
- Apartment
- Prefer not to say

Follow-up question (If question 13 answer is “Apartment”):

13.a. On which floor?

----- (a drop list)

14. When was your house built?

- Before 2010
- In 2010 or after
- I do not know
- Prefer not to say

15. Do you own the house you currently live in in Al Ain city?

- Yes, I am the homeowner
- No, I am a renter
- Prefer not to say

Follow-up question (If question 15 answer is “No, I am a renter”):

15.a. Do you or someone in your household pay the home rent?

- Yes
- No
- Prefer not to say

Follow-up question (If question 15.a. answer is “Yes”):

15.a.a. Who is the home rent paid to?

- Bank
- Homeowner
- The company or institution you work for
- Other
- Prefer not to say

Follow-up question (If question 15.a.a. answer is “Other”):

15.a.a.a. Please specify.

16. How many bedrooms do you have in your home?

----- (a drop list)

17. Do you or someone in your household pay the electricity bills?

- Yes
- No

- Prefer not to say

18. What is the approximate family's monthly income? (AED = UAE Dirham)

- Income is less than 5,000 AED
- Income is equal to or more than 5,000 AED and less than 10,000 AED
- Income is equal to or more than 10,000 AED and less than 15,000 AED
- Income is equal to or more than 15,000 AED and less than 20,000 AED
- Income is equal to or more than 20,000 AED and less than 25,000 AED
- Income is equal to or more than 25,000 AED and less than 30,000 AED
- Income is equal to or more than 30,000 AED and less than 35,000 AED
- Income is equal to or more than 35,000 AED
- Other
- Prefer not to say

Follow-up question (If question 18 answer is "Other"):

18.a. Please specify.

Part 2:

19. In your opinion, your electricity bills are a

- Significant proportion of the monthly income
- Quite significant proportion of the monthly income
- I am not sure
- Not quite significant proportion of the monthly income
- Insignificant proportion of the monthly income
- Prefer not to say

20. How do you feel at home in general during summer season under typical circumstances (Example: with air conditioning runs on at home)?

- Cold
- Cool
- Slightly cool
- Neutral
- Slightly warm
- Warm
- Hot
- Prefer not to say

21. In your opinion, does your home have typically an acceptable temperature during summer season?

- Clearly acceptable
- Just acceptable
- Just unacceptable
- Clearly unacceptable
- Prefer not to say

Follow-up question (If question 21 answer is “Just unacceptable” or “Clearly unacceptable”):

21.a. Please explain why.

22. Would you prefer to have your home:

- Much cooler
- Cooler
- Slightly cooler
- Without change
- Slightly warmer
- Warmer
- Much warmer
- Prefer not to say

23. What is the first thing do you usually do when you feel hot at home during summer season?

- Turn on the air conditioning
- Turn on the fan
- Open the window
- Close curtains
- Drink cold water
- Reduce clothing layers
- Take a shower
- Other
- Prefer not to say

Follow-up question (If question 23 answer is “Other”):

23.a. Please specify.

24. What type of air conditioning do you have at your home? *Please choose all options that apply, and refer to the attached pictures for the different types of air conditioning.*

- Central air conditioning

- Split air conditioning

- Window air conditioning

- There is no air conditioning in my home
- Prefer not to say

25. Please tick the spaces where do you have air conditioning in your home? *Please choose all options that apply.*

- Bedrooms
- Living room
- Dining room
- Kitchen
- Corridors
- Bathrooms
- Storage
- Prefer not to say

26. How do you change the air conditioning setting temperature?

- Through a remote controller
- I set the air conditioning on the automatic mode
- I have a smart controller
- I control the air conditioning through internet
- I cannot change the setting temperature of the air conditioning (Go directly to question 30)
- Other
- Prefer not to say

Follow-up question (If question 26 answer is “Other”):

26.a. Please specify.

27. At what temperature do you usually set your air conditioning during summer season? (*°C = Degree Celsius*)

----- (*a drop list*)

28. Do you always keep the air conditioning setting at the same temperature?

- Yes
- Depends
- No
- Prefer not to say

Follow-up question (If question 28 answer is “Depends” or “No”):

28.a. Please explain why.

29. Are you able to control the air conditioning in each room separately?

- Yes, I can turn the air conditioning on/off and change temperature in each room
- No, there is a shared control between two or more rooms/spaces
- I only have one room/space with air conditioning unit in my home
- Prefer not to say

30. Do you usually turn the air conditioning on and off only once a day in your home?

- Yes, I usually turn it on and off only one time in a day
- No, I usually turn it on and off multiple times in a day
- Prefer not to say

Follow-up question (If question 30 answer is “No, I usually turn it on and off multiple times in a day”):

30.a. Please explain when do you usually turn on and off the air conditioning in your home during summer season? (*Answer example: I usually turn it on on weekdays from 2:00 pm until 6:00 pm and then turn it on again from 9:00 pm until 7:00 am next day. In weekends, I usually turn it on from 6:00 pm until 8:00 pm and from 11:00 pm until 3:00 pm next day.*)

Follow-up questions (If question 30 answer is “Yes, I usually turn it on and off only one time in a day”):

30.b. From what time to what time do you normally turn the air conditioning on on weekdays?

From what time?

----- (a drop list)

Until what time?

----- (a drop list)

30.c. From what time to what time do you normally turn the air conditioning on on weekend?

From what time?

----- (a drop list)

Until what time?

----- (a drop list)

31. From what time to what time is usually the home empty (no one is at home) during the weekdays?

From what time?

----- (a drop list)

Until what time?

----- (a drop list)

32. From what time to what time is usually the home empty (no one is at home) during the **weekend**?

From what time?

----- (a drop list)

Until what time?

----- (a drop list)

33. Do you usually travel or leave home for any reason during summer holiday or summer months?

- Yes
- Sometimes
- No
- Prefer not to say

Follow-up question (If question 33 answer is “Yes” or “Sometimes”):

33.a. From what time to what time do you usually leave home/travel during summer holiday or summer months?

From what time?

----- (a drop list)

Until what time?

----- (a drop list)

Follow-up question (If question 33.a. answer is “Other”):

33.a.a. Please specify.

34. Do you usually leave the air conditioning on when you leave the room?

- Yes, I usually leave the air conditioning on when I leave the room
- Sometimes I leave the air conditioning on when I leave the room
- No, I always turn off the air conditioning when I leave the room
- The air conditioning runs on a timer
- I control the air conditioning through internet
- The air conditioning runs through smart control
- Prefer not to say

Follow-up question (If question 34 answer is “The air conditioning runs through smart control”):

34.a. Please explain how the air conditioning is controlled when the smart control mode is used?

35. Are any of the air conditioning units left on in any room when no one is at home? *Please choose all options that apply.*

- Usually we leave one or more air conditioning units turned on when we leave the home

- Sometimes we leave one or more air conditioning units turned on when we leave for a holiday or travel
- Sometimes we ask a relative or a friend to turn on one or more air conditioning units in the home when we leave for a holiday or travel
- No, all air conditioning units are turned off when no one is at home
- The air conditioning runs on a timer
- The air conditioning is controlled through internet
- The air conditioning runs through smart control
- Prefer not to say

36. Do you have fans in your home?

- Yes, I have fans and I use them
- Yes, I have fans, but I do not use them
- No, I do not have fans in my home
- Prefer not to say

37. How do you ventilate your home during summer season? *Please choose all options that apply.*

- Opening windows
- Opening doors
- Using extract fan in the kitchen and/or bathrooms
- Opening vents on windows frames
- I cannot ventilate my home
- Prefer not to say

38. When do you usually ventilate your home during summer season? *Please choose all options that apply.*

- Whenever I want to freshen the air in the room or home
- While sleeping at night
- While cooking
- While taking a shower
- Before using the air conditioning
- While using the air conditioning
- After using the air conditioning
- I cannot ventilate my home
- Prefer not to say

39. When do you usually turn on artificial lights in your home?

- When I come back home from work / school / university / ...
- When it becomes dark
- When I wake up in the morning
- Before I sleep
- I always leave the artificial lights on
- I control lights remotely through internet
- I use smart control
- I have smart sensors in my home in which lights turn on automatically
- Other

- Prefer not to say

Follow-up question (If question 39 answer is “I use smart control”):

39.a. Please explain how artificial lights are controlled when the smart control mode is used?

Follow-up question (If question 39 answer is “Other”):

39.b. Please specify.

40. Which of these appliances **do not** you have in your home? *Please choose all options that apply.*

- Refrigerator
- Washer
- Dryer
- Dishwasher
- Kettle
- Iron
- Stove and oven
- Microwave
- Grill
- Toaster
- Hairdryer
- Television
- Laptop and/or computer
- Gaming appliances (Example: PlayStation, ...)
- Water heater
- Grass mower
- Prefer not to say

41. What other appliances do you have at your home that are not mentioned in the list above?

42. How do you characterize your behavior with regards to electricity consumption at home?

- I do not pay much attention to my electricity consumption
- I tend to reduce my electricity consumption
- I consider my electricity consumption to be average
- I do not know
- Prefer not to say

43. If I could, I would *(Please choose all options that apply)*

- Buy more energy efficient home appliances
- Replace the current appliances
- Pay more attention to how much electricity I use
- Pay less attention to how much electricity I use
- Ask for help of a professional in energy saving ways and techniques

- Install smart meter at home to track my consumption
- I would not change anything
- I do not know
- Prefer not to say

44. What would this depend upon? *Please choose all options that apply.*

- Having more money available
- Having more space available at home
- Having more time to monitor electricity use
- Having more time to spend at home
- Having to work from home
- Having more information about energy efficiency
- I do not know
- Prefer not to say

45. If you had the chance to change anything in the way you use electricity and the air conditioning system in your home, what would it be? *Please choose all options that apply.*

- Always turn off the air conditioning when I leave the room or home
- Change the air conditioning type
- Improve the air conditioning efficiency to bring cooler air
- Change the air conditioning controller type
- Raise the air conditioning setting temperature
- Lower the air conditioning setting temperature
- Try to be thermally comfortable in other ways instead of using the air conditioning
- I do not know
- Prefer not to say

46. Please write here if you would like to change anything else in the way you use electricity and the air conditioning system in your home that is not mentioned in the list above.

As part of this Ph.D. research, interviews will be carried out with a number of expatriate housing users living in Al Ain city (in person or online) for further data collection. If you would like to participate as an interviewee, please feel free to write your email address here and I will contact you to schedule an interview according to your availability. Please note that if you choose to write your email, it will not be shared with anyone except the research team.

End of survey!